

Relationship Between Singing and Blood Urine Level

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ABSTRACT

If someone is too much addicted to singing their brain may release some sort of chemicals that may cause urine in blood (hematuria). The examination was done among 90 students belonging to Bahauddin Zakariya University Multan. It involves testing each and every student and then noting their opinions on singing in a separate form. From the data collected, various results and the relation between singing and blood in urine was derived. Although no link between these two can be seen but hematuria can be regarded as an uncommon disease. It can be due to various causes and can be examined by performing urinalysis test.

Keywords: Singing, Hematuria, Antibiotics.

1. Introduction

The word hematuria is used to name the condition of blood in urine. It can be an indication that kidneys or urinary tract is facing some problem. Hematuria can be of two types. It can be termed as gross hematuria if the blood is visible in urine. And if the blood that is not visible in urine can only be recognized under electron microscope [1-2]. In that case. It can be termed as microscopic hematuria. Various reason can cause this disease. People who have ancestral record of having kidney stones or kidney disease are more prone to this disease. Excessive exercise or being on medication such as pain relievers can also cause this disease.

Various elements can result blood in urine like certain virus or infection. Tiring exercise or some sort of injury can also cause it. Sickle cell or polycystic kidney diseases are also some of its causes. For the symptoms of this disease, you will observe pink, red or brown pigment in the urine.

In some cases, aching blood clots can be felt too. Different treatment can be conducted depending on the source of the disease. Antibiotics can be used for treating infections.

Singing is employing the vocals in a melodic way which can be appealing to the listener. Music can be of various types like pop, rock, opera. Singing have various benefits. It can help to upgrade and nourish your vocals. It can minimize stress and relax your brain.

If someone is too much addicted to singing their brain may release some sort of chemicals that may cause urine in blood(hematuria). Better sleep, improved posture and mental attentiveness are also some of its benefits [3-5].

2. Materials and Methods

The test was carried out among 90 students belonging to the Bahauddin Zakariya University Multan varying between the age from 18 to 22. This test does not need extra requirements. The patient just needs to avoid in taking any food before several hours of test. Cleansing pad, container are the materials required. The patient needs to wash his hands before the test.

Blood in urine measurement

Urinalysis can be conducted to check the presence of blood in the urine. This test analyze urine for various cells, chemicals and blood. First of all, hands are washed. Cleansing pad can be used to sterilize the genital area. The patient had to gather the urine in a container provided. Markings are present on the container to collect the required amount. This container is then presented to the laboratory to find the cause of the blood in urine.

Dipstick instrument can also be used to detect various changes in urine.

Study design

Out of 90 students 21 males and 69 females were involved. Among the male population, 11 of them did not showed up for singing while rest of them liked singing. Among the female population, 25 of them disliked singing while rest of 44 females liked singing. This analysis was entirely based on each and every student likeness.

Statistical Analysis

Statistix software gives results accurately and this was used to conduct this experiment. p value holds great importance in analyzing the results. If its value is less than 0.1, it is considered as notable.

3. Result and Discussions

Gender	Singing Likeness		Singing Dis-likeness	
	Presence of blood urine	Absence of blood in urine	Presence of blood in urine	Absence of blood in urine
Male	1	10	2	8
Female	8	41	4	16

The above table illustrates that this is not so common disease. Only small amount of people is affected by this disease [6-8]. One 1 male is affected by this disease who liked singing. While 8 females have this disease out of 41 strength. From the category of singing dis likeness, 2 males and 4 females are affected by this disease. 24 students from singing dis likeness are marked safe from this category. Questionnaire studies are important in finding out results and illustrating the data and helpful in analysis [9-10].

4. Conclusion

To conclude, this study didn't show any resemblance between singing and blood in urine. The probability of this disease was relatively less. There were more chances of it in female than in men. Out of total strength, 18.6 percent students were infected by this disease.

Declarations

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Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no competing financial, professional, or personal interests.

Ethical Approval

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan.

Consent for publication

The authors declare that they consented to the publication of this research work.

Availability of data and material

The authors are willing to share the data and material according to relevant needs.

References

- [1] Qadir MI, Malik SA. (2010). Comparison of alterations in red blood cell count and alterations in hemoglobin concentration in patients suffering from rectal carcinoma undergoing 5-fluorouracil and folic acid therapy. *Pharmacologyonline*, N1 3: 240-243.
- [2] Qadir MI, Noor A. (2018). *Anemias. Rare & Uncommon Diseases*. Cambridge Scholars Publishing. Newcastle, England, ISBN: 978-1-5275-1807-0.
- [3] Brown RS. (2011). Has the time come to include urine dipstick testing in screening asymptomatic young adults? *JAMA*, 306: 764–5.
- [4] Fradet Y. (2009). Screening for bladder cancer: the best opportunity to reduce mortality. *Canadian Urological Association Journal*, 3: S180–3.
- [5] Pashayan N, Khogali M, Major SC. (2002). Routine urinalysis of patients in hospital in Lebanon: how worthwhile is it. *J Med Screen.*, 9: 181–6.
- [6] Vivante A, Afek A, Frenkel-Nir Y, et al. (2011). Persistent asymptomatic isolated microscopic hematuria in Israeli adolescents and young adults and risk for end-stage renal disease. *JAMA*, 306: 729–36.
- [7] Moore GP, Robinson M. (1988). Do urine dipsticks reliably predict microhematuria? The bloody truth! *Ann Emerg Med.*, 17: 257–60.
- [8] Rao PK, Gao T, Pohl M, Jones JS. (2010). Dipstick pseudohematuria: unnecessary consultation and evaluation. *Journal of Urology*, 183: 560–4.
- [9] European COLM. (2000). European urinalysis guidelines. *Scand J Clin Lab Invest Suppl.*, 231: 1–86.
- [10] Silkensen JR, Kasike BL. (2004). Laboratory assessment of renal disease: clearance, urinalysis, and renal biopsy. In: Brenner BM, editor. *The kidney*. 7th ed. Philadelphia: Saunders, pp. 1107–50.